

First record of *Lasiocoris crassicornis* (Lucas, 1849) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae) in Montenegro

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ABSTRACT: The first record of *Lasiocoris crassicornis* (Lucas, 1849) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Megalonotini) for Montenegro is reported. Information on the known distribution of the species is summarised.

KEYWORDS: *Lasiocoris crassicornis*, first record, distribution, Montenegro, Mediterranean Region.

So far, the rhyparochromid *Lasiocoris crassicornis* (Lucas, 1849) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Megalonotini) has been reported from Albania, Andorra, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, France, Greece (including Crete), Italy (Sardinia and Sicily), North Macedonia, Romania, Russia (South-European part), Spain and Turkey (European part) in Europe; Algeria, Libya, Morocco and Tunisia in Northern Africa and Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Israel, Lebanon, Syria and Turkey (Asian part) in Asia (Protić, 1987 (as *L. antennatus* Montandon, 1889); Péricart, 1999, 2001; Linnavuori, 2007; Ghahari & Moulet, 2012; van der Heyden & Dioli, 2020; Ghahari et al., 2024).

Herein, the first record of *L. crassicornis* in Montenegro is reported: On 11.05.2017, an adult specimen of the species (Fig. 1) was found near the city of Cetinje, located

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at the foot of the Lovćen massif (coordinates: 42.3560492, 19.0165687). The specimen is stored in the collection of Arto Muinonen (pers. comm.). A photo of the specimen was uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Muinonen, 2026).

Figure 1. Specimen of *Lasiocoris crassicornis* (Lucas, 1849), near Cetinje, Montenegro, 11.05.2017. (Photo: Arto Muinonen).

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